

Reconfigurable Pipeline Skeleton for Parallel Applications Codesign on High-Performance Heterogeneous Computing Systems

Carlos Alfonso Acosta-León¹[0000–0003–1895–4040]
and Rina Surós²[0000–0001–6443–9889]

Laboratorio de Computación Heterogénea de Alto Rendimiento (LabCHAR)
Centro de Computación Paralela y Distribuida, Escuela de Computación
Universidad Central de Venezuela, Los Chaguaramos, Caracas 1040-A, Venezuela.
cacostal@yahoo.co.uk, carlos.acosta@ucv.ve¹
rsuros@gmail.com, rina.suros@ciens.ucv.ve²

Abstract. Reconfigurable heterogeneous computing systems (RHCS) have been used to exploit parallelism by means of coupled and coordinated processing between FPGA and different microprogrammable computing devices. However, these systems have high programming complexity due to the details associated with parallelism and FPGA logic design. Therefore, the development of the hardware and software components of an application at the same level of abstraction has been difficult to achieve. Several techniques have been described in the literature that attempt to reduce such complexity to the programmer, but without achieving sufficient transparency and abstraction. In this paper we introduce a reconfigurable pattern of parallel ‘pipeline’ computing, called *PipeSkeleton*. It is an algorithmic skeleton provided as a high-level template in OpenCL code. As a demonstration, a tests suite with different configurations integrating hardware and software components are described. It was shown that configurations with hardware-implemented kernels and software-implemented data input/output run faster and consume fewer resources. As conclusion, the tool provides to the programmer the abstraction level to easily move functionalities between software and hardware during the exploration stage of application design spaces.

Keywords: Heterogeneous Reconfigurable Computing · Parallelism · FPGA · Algorithmic Skeletons · Hardware/Software Co-design.

1 Introduction

This paper focuses on Reconfigurable Heterogeneous Computing Systems (RHCS) based on Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) computing devices. Reconfigurable Heterogeneous Computing Systems, described by Zahran in [11], integrate different processing elements, both structurally and functionally, into a single computational system in a way that is transparent to the user. This makes it possible to incorporate specialized processing capabilities to accelerate tasks in

a particular field or area in order to significantly increase performance. However, the problem with RHCS is that they bring high programming complexity [8]. This is because the parallel applications development in these systems requires the integration and coordination of tasks running on software and hardware. This means that the programmer has to pay attention to low-level details associated with parallelism [9], and also to the structural and functional details associated to FPGA logic design [6].

Finally, in this research paper we propose a co-design and programming tool based on reconfigurable algorithmic skeletons. This tool provides the programmer with structured and reconfigurable parallelism for the hardware/software co-design of parallel applications.

2 Related Research Work

In the literature there are works that propose Libraries, APIs or Frameworks of parallel computing patterns encapsulated as algorithmic skeletons. One work oriented to heterogeneous computing systems comes from the SkelCL project [10]. This is a library of algorithmic skeletons implemented using the OpenCL language, portable to different heterogeneous CPU-GPU systems. This library is composed of four parallel skeleton models: Map, Zip, Reduce and Scan, which operate on one-dimensional vectors on CPU and GPU, although not transparently. In the same direction, in a recent work, Ernstsson et al. propose SkePU [4], an open source CPU-GPU heterogeneous system programming framework for multicore CPUs and multi-GPU systems. They are C++ templates with data parallelism skeletons, with support for execution on multi-GPU systems with both CUDA and OpenCL and clustered execution. However, these projects do not incorporate hardware skeletons for heterogeneous CPU-GPU-FPGA architectures.

The HeteroCL project by Lai et al. [7] is one among few works where a programming infrastructure composed of a domain-specific language (DSL) based on Python with CPU, GPU and FPGA oriented compilation is proposed. It provides abstraction through programming that decouples the algorithm specification from the computing architecture hardware. Also, it allows the programmer to explore performance systematically with hardware implementations using systolic array templates and dataflow stencils. However, the tool does not consider the hardware/software tasks co-design of a parallel application at the same level of abstraction.

Based on the reviewed works, there are few oriented to facilitate hardware/software co-design and programming of system-level parallel applications on heterogeneous computing platforms with CPU-GPU-FPGA. In addition, some reviewed works assume that the programmer has some knowledge of reconfigurable computing system architecture, details associated with parallelism and FPGA design.

3 Preliminary Background

Although there are several high-level abstraction techniques for design and programming, in this research work we are interested in those that allow hiding and encapsulating parallelism. From these design and programming techniques, Cole’s algorithmic skeletons and the hardware/software co-design have been chosen. They are the foundation for the design of the proposed tool that integrates them into a solution or framework called SkeletonCoRe.

Applications development for heterogeneous architecture computing systems involve code sections that are usually designed and implemented separately in hardware and software, using different tools and techniques, and by different people. So, Co-design [1, 5] is a methodology that integrates the cooperative design of hardware and software sections of an application. However, it does not guarantee that these sections are developed at the same level of abstraction, which makes it difficult to migrate functionality between software and hardware. As a solution to this problem, we have proposed the use of algorithmic skeletons in the co-design process. This approach allows the development of such components at the same level of abstraction and the transparent movement of functionalities between CPUs, GPUs and FPGAs.

Cole [2, 3] introduced Algorithmic Skeletons as a mechanism for encapsulating and reusing parallelism. They are an abstraction structured approach that allows separating a parallel computing pattern from its implementation in a particular computing architecture. Skeletons hide the explicit details of parallel programming from the programmer and make possible an appropriate and efficient solution to a specific problem.

4 PipeSkeleton: A Reconfigurable Pipeline Skeleton

Algorithmic skeletons, hardware/software co-design, FPGAs and the OpenCL language are integrated into a framework, called SkeletonCoRe. This high-level framework provides a catalog of reconfigurable algorithmic skeletons oriented to the parallel applications co-design and programming on reconfigurable heterogeneous computing systems. Here, a skeleton is implemented as a higher-order function through sequential code templates, with data and functions as parameters, coded using OpenCL language. These parameters internally define its parallel behavior. Each skeleton transparently coordinates the interaction between software tasks on CPU-GPU and hardware tasks on FPGA.

As a proof-of-concept, we introduce and evaluate the cost of a reconfigurable algorithmic skeleton, denoted as “*PipeSkeleton*” “Reconfigurable Pipeline Skeleton”. This algorithmic skeleton is an instance from the reconfigurable skeletons catalog of the SkeletonCoRe Framework.

This skeleton implements the well-known pipelined parallel processing pattern called “*pipeline*” in which a “stream” of data elements flows through a sequence of stages (ordered like a pipeline) where in each one an operation or task is applied to each element of the stream. This behavior can be described

as follows, $f : \alpha \rightarrow \beta$ on a “stream” of input values a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n which implies a composition over n functions $f_1 \dots f_n$ such that $f_1 : a_1 \rightarrow \gamma_1, \dots, f_i : \gamma_{i-1} \rightarrow \gamma_i, \dots, f_n : \gamma_{n-1} \rightarrow \beta$. The idea is to exploit parallelism from processing on different elements of the “input stream” (without data dependencies).

PipeSkeleton is a higher-order template that is instantiated with several parameters, between data and behavior (As is shown for the pseudocodes in Fig. 1). That is, the size of the hardware and software partitions, an array of tasks for each pipeline stage and the data segments size. This skeleton manages the pipeline through two partitions, one in software (CPU-GPU) and one in hardware (FPGA), both with defined sizes and whose sum conforms the total length of the pipeline. To each pipeline stage corresponds a specific task for processing, including input and output tasks. The communication interface that connects the software partition on the host computer with the hardware partition on the FPGA board is transparent to the programmer.

<pre> include "openc1.h" include "skeltoncore.h" /* Global declaration */ FILE *List_imagesIn, *List_imagesOut; int segment_size; main (argc, argv[]) { /* Pipeline size */ int cpu_pipesize, gpu_pipesize, fpga_pipesize; /* Create heterogeneous pipeline */ device_type "device_cpu","device_gpu","device_fpga"; func_type "tasks_List[cpu_pipesize+gpu_pipesize+fpga_pipesize]; /*----- Program body -----*/ /* Setting up the SkeletonCore Framework */ SkeletonCore_init(); /* Getting the PipeSkeleton size */ skc_read(cpu_pipesize, gpu_pipesize, fpga_pipesize); if (cpu_pipesize > 0) (gpu_pipesize > 0) (fpga_pipesize > 0) { /* Getting the tasks for the stages of PipeSkeleton */ skc_getTasks(tasks_List[task_1, task_2, ..., task_n]); /* Reading the image source file */ skc_getData(List_imagesIn); /* Creates instance of PipeSkeleton */ myPipe = new skc_PipeSkeleton(); /* Invoke PipeSkeleton for image processing */ myPipe->device_cpu, "device_gpu, "device_fpga, "tasks_List[], *List_imagesIn, *List_imagesOut, segment_size); /* Writing the output image file */ skc_putOutcomes(List_imageOut); } else { print("Pipeline not defined!"); } /* Finalizing the SkeletonCore Framework */ SkeletonCore_finalize(); } </pre>	<pre> void PipeSkeleton("device_cpu, "device_gpu, "device_fpga, "tasks_List[], *List_imagesIn, *List_imagesOut, segment_size) { cl_uint num_devices_returned; cl_device_id devices[3]; channel float cpu_gpu_channel, gpu_fpga_channel, fpga_cpu_channel; func_type "cpu_Tasks, "gpu_Tasks, "fpga_Tasks; cpu_Task = &tasks_List[cpu_pipesize]; gpu_Task = &tasks_List[gpu_pipesize]; fpga_Task = &tasks_List[fpga_pipesize]; /* Get the device(s) */ err = clGetDeviceIDs(NULL, CL_DEVICE_TYPE_GPU, 1, &devices[0], &num_devices_returned); err = clGetDeviceIDs(NULL, CL_DEVICE_TYPE_CPU, 1, &devices[1], &num_devices_returned); err = clGetDeviceIDs(NULL, CL_DEVICE_TYPE_FPGA, 1, &devices[2], &num_devices_returned); /* Create contexts for devices */ cl_context context; context = clCreateContext(0, 3, devices, NULL, NULL, &err); /* Create commands queue for devices */ cl_command_queue queue_gpu, queue_cpu, queue_fpga; device_gpu = clCreateCommandQueue(context, devices[0], 0, &err); device_cpu = clCreateCommandQueue(context, devices[1], 0, &err); device_fpga = clCreateCommandQueue(context, devices[2], 0, &err); /* Basic pipeline for PieSkeleton */ kernel void cpu(global int* in) { for (int i = 0; i < workload_size; ++i) { int "image_segment" = read_Image(); value[segment_size] = cpu_Tasks[image_segment, 0, 255]; // do some work write_channel(cpu_gpu_channel, &value); // send data to the next partition } } kernel void gpu() { for (int i = 0; i < workload_size; ++i) { int value = read_channel(cpu_gpu_channel); // take data from cpu value[segment_size] = gpu_Tasks[image_segment, 0, 255]; // do some work write_channel(gpu_fpga_channel, &value); // send data to the next partition } } kernel void fpga(global int* out) { for (int i = 0; i < workload_size; ++i) { int value = read_channel(gpu_fpga_channel); // take data from gpu value[segment_size] = fpga_Tasks[image_segment, 0, 255]; // do some work write_channel(fpga_cpu_channel, &value); // write result in the end } } /* Start concurrently tasks (kernels) for partitions in CPU-GPU-FPGA */ clEnqueueTask(device_cpu, "TasksList[cpu_size]); clEnqueueTask(device_gpu, "TasksList[gpu_size]); clEnqueueTask(device_fpga, "TasksList[fpga_size]); clFinish(device_fpga); // last kernels in our pipeline } </pre>
a) Source pseudocode for using PipeSkeleton	b) OpenCL pseudocode for implementing PipeSkeleton

Fig. 1. Examples of OpenCL pseudocode for PipeSkeleton.

5 Functionality tests for PipeSkeleton

5.1 Development Platform specifications

To evaluate our tool we have used a reconfigurable heterogeneous computing platform consisting of an AsRock motherboard supporting an Intel® Core™ 10th Gen i5-1040F processor with 6 cores (12 threads) at 2.9 GHz and two banks of DDR4 memory of 8 GB each at 2933 MHz. The motherboard is equipped with an Intel® Stratix® 10 GX FPGA board with 10.2 million Logic Elements (LEs) and an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1060 graphics card with 1280 cores and 6GB of memory. All these devices are connected via a 64-bit system bus. In addition,

the heterogeneous computing system uses Linux Ubuntu version 20.04.4 LTS, and GCC version 9.4.0 to compile the Host (CPU-GPU) and FPGA codes in openCL language version 1.0. The application development environment for the heterogeneous system is Quartus version 22.1.0 with Intel FPGA SDK for OpenCL version 22.1. Based on the architecture of the SkeletonCoRe framework we have chosen Intel® Quartus® Prime Design Software and Intel FPGA SDK for OpenCL because they cover the four lower layers and therefore provide the functionalities associated with the process of compiling the components for the CPU and GPU (scheduling) and the synthesis (partitioning, placement and routing) of the components for the FPGA.

5.2 Description of Functionality Tests

A set of experiments have been prepared to test the functionality and performance of PipeSkeleton. We have implemented a parallel application composed of a queue of image operators whose kernels are assigned as tasks to each stage of the pipeline. The order of precedence of these image operators is fixed, and they are as follows: \rightarrow Interpolation \rightarrow Sobel's Edge Detection \rightarrow Sum \rightarrow Thresholding \rightarrow Sum \rightarrow . In addition, the test workload is composed of four lists of 256 images each with dimensions of 256x256, 512x512, 1024x1024 and 2048x2048 pixels, respectively, to exploit data parallelism.

In Fig. 2 can be seen the configurations used to perform the performance and functionality test of *PipeSkeleton*. As test configurations (experiments), pipeline partitions (stages) of the form CPU-GPU-FPGA into our heterogeneous computing system have been performed. So, as an initial and reference configuration for performance comparison, the entire pipeline of our parallel application (five stages) has been mapped as software tasks only on CPU (5-0-0 or CPU-0-0), instead of the best sequential code. Then, only on GPU (0-5-0 or 0-GPU-0) (see Fig. 2a) and also, the entire pipeline has been mapped as hardware tasks only on the FPGA device (0-0-5 or 0-0-FPGA) (see Fig. 2b).

Finally, a intermediate configuration combinations of partitions with software and hardware tasks or kernels of the pipeline have been distributed and mapped between the GPU and the FPGA (0-GPU-FPGA) respectively, always keeping the precedence order of the image operators in the pipeline (see Fig. 2c). In all test configurations, both benchmark and intermediate, the data read and write tasks have been fixedly mapped to CPU only.

5.3 Funtionality Test Results

The results of the tests are shown in Table 1 and introduces the processing times of four lists of 256 images of dimensions 256x256, 512x512, 1024x1024 and 2048x2048 pixels. Each image is divided into two-line or two-row image data segments for processing. Processing times are observed when PipeSkeleton is implemented on CPU only (5-0-0). These times are taken as a reference in determining the computational speedup with respect to the times of PipeSkeleton configured on GPU only (0-5-0), FPGA only (0-0-5) and hardware/software partitioning combinations between GPU and FPGA (0-X-X).

Fig. 2. Mapping PipeSkeleton on the heterogeneous reconfigurable computing system.

Table 1. Comparison of processing time for computing devices CPU, GPU and FPGA.

Partition (CPU-GPU-FPGA)	Image size (pixels)	Segments x image	Workload (segments x all images)	Total time x segment (milise)	Total time x image (milise)	- With skeleton - Total time x workload (miliseconds)	- No skeleton - Total time x workload (miliseconds)	Skeleton overhead (milise)	Total Cost of FPGA LU Ts	Speed-Up with skeleton %
5-0-0	256 x 256	128	32768	1.640625	43.312500	10753.312500	10753.204967	0.107533	0	1.00
	512 x 512	256	65536	2.985938	155.268750	39139.668750	39139.277353	0.391397	0	1.00
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	5.434406	560.830725	142464.046725	142462.622085	1.424640	0	1.00
0-5-0	256 x 256	128	32768	0.032471	0.857227	212.825977	212.823848	0.002128	0	50.53
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.058447	3.039258	766.126758	766.119097	0.007661	0	51.09
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.105205	10.857164	2757.972164	2757.944584	0.027580	0	51.66
0-4-1	256 x 256	128	32768	0.199890	41.097312	10480.134312	10480.029510	0.104801	0	49.48
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.025618	0.828670	207.219295	207.217223	0.002072	1023	51.89
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.045607	2.915727	737.666352	737.658975	0.007377	2044	53.06
0-3-2	256 x 256	128	32768	0.081193	10.318853	2626.031078	2626.004818	0.026260	4084	54.25
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.155573	39.506656	10083.841600	10083.740761	0.100838	8159	51.42
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.022633	0.636413	158.382601	158.381017	0.001584	7161	67.89
0-2-3	256 x 256	128	32768	0.040450	2.234108	563.810536	563.804898	0.005638	14307	69.42
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.072294	7.897029	2007.109111	2007.089040	0.020071	28586	70.98
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.125386	28.321994	7225.485488	7225.413234	0.072255	57115	71.77
0-1-4	256 x 256	128	32768	0.021395	0.605161	150.637599	150.636092	0.001506	8184	71.39
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.038328	2.124716	536.240194	536.234831	0.005362	16351	72.99
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.068663	7.510770	1908.961870	1908.942780	0.019090	32670	74.63
0-0-5	256 x 256	128	32768	0.115311	26.337161	6719.445032	6719.377838	0.067194	65274	77.17
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.020748	0.589507	146.765070	146.763602	0.001468	14322	73.27
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.037257	2.070011	522.455013	522.449789	0.005225	28615	74.91
0-0-5	256 x 256	128	32768	0.066903	7.317696	1859.888305	1859.869706	0.018599	57172	76.60
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.108099	23.333340	5951.559289	5951.499773	0.059516	114229	87.13
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.020337	0.536895	133.296270	133.294937	0.001333	18414	80.67
0-0-5	256 x 256	128	32768	0.036606	1.903535	479.837285	479.832487	0.004798	36790	81.57
	512 x 512	256	65536	0.065892	6.800013	1727.361513	1727.344240	0.017274	73507	82.47
	1024 x 1024	512	131072	0.106744	21.946648	5596.565908	5596.509942	0.055966	146866	92.66

Legend: For our workload we get the experimental data from four list of 256 images each x 2 lines x image segment.

6 Results Discussion

Based on the results obtained and shown in Table 1, a significant increase of Speed-Up is observed in the GPU benchmark tests up to 50%, and FPGA benchmark tests up to 92%, with respect to the execution times of PipeSkeleton running only on CPU. Likewise, it is observed that intermediate tests with combinations of PipeSkeleton partitions with fewer stages on GPU and more stages on FPGA show a progressive and significant increase of Speed-Up between 51.42% and 87.13% with respect to CPU times. These tests also demonstrate the possibility to explore parallel application design spaces and choose the configuration with the best performance and efficiency.

However, we also noticed a small difference (overhead) between the processing times when using the encapsulation provided by the PipeSkeleton algorithmic

skeleton (which provides implicit parallelism) with respect to when using the parallel application without the algorithmic skeleton (explicit parallelism).

Similarly, there is an additional hardware resource cost in logic elements (4-input LUTs, without optimization) when implementing the PipeSkeleton partition on FPGA. The implementation of filters, registers and data vectors of the size of the image segment to be processed is the reason for the high utilization of logic elements (4-input LUTs) of the FPGA. Moreover, the cost of FPGA LUTs is proportional to the size of the problem, i.e., to the size of the image segments or vectors and to the complexity of the tasks or kernels of the pipeline partitions that are implemented in the FPGA.

Another observation, obtained from Table 1, refers to the fact that the pipeline stage with the highest latency constituted an appreciable bottleneck in processing on CPU and GPU, but very little on FPGA. Also, we consider that the 1280-core GPU limit (NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1060 card) reduced the processing time of the 2048x2048 pixel image list, where the Speed-Up was reduced from 50.53% to 49.48%.

Finally, since the CPU and both the GPU and FPGA boards are connected to the heterogeneous computing system via a 64-bit high-speed bus, low communication latency was observed in the data transfer of the 256 images used in each test image list.

7 Conclusions and Future Work

We have shown the use and utility of PipeSkeleton. Skeleton approach has allowed to implement parallelism and reconfiguration easily, transparently and independently of the available computing platform with high performance.

Tests have been performed with different configurations integrating hardware and software tasks. In each configuration we have measured the cost in execution time and amount of resources used. It has been shown that configurations with FPGA-implemented kernels and CPU-implemented data input/output tasks run faster and consume fewer resources.

In addition, the time overhead and FPGA resources used in the implementation of the skeleton is relatively small. Although the resources allocated by the language to encapsulate the parallel pattern using a template with parameters makes this cost almost constant and independent of the size of the problem managed by the PipeSkeleton skeleton.

However, the cost of the abstraction provided by the skeletons may result in a small loss of efficiency compared to explicitly parallel code written by experts. Still, the skeleton abstraction can lead to higher productivity and performance because the parallelism structuring can enable automated optimizations. In addition, this abstraction provides the programmer with the ability to easily move functionality between software and hardware during the exploration stage of application design spaces.

As additional work, it is necessary to extend the library of skeletons that implement other parallel computing patterns such as map & reduce, divide &

conquer, tasks farm, data farm, etc. Also, tests should be performed with more demanding applications in terms of computing power, such as those in the area of cryptography or numerical simulation, for example, to evaluate the functionality and stress the performance of the skeletons.

Acknowledgements The first author of this article is very grateful to his supervisor, Dr. Murray I. Cole, for his invaluable mentoring, help and support during his PhD in Informatics at the University of Edinburgh, Scotland-UK. He would also like to thank his co-supervisor Dr. Rina Surós at the UCV for her unconditional support.

References

1. Cardoso, J.M.P., (auth.), M.H.: Reconfigurable Computing: From FPGAs to Hardware/Software Codesign. Springer-Verlag New York, 1st edition edn. (2011)
2. Cole, M.: Algorithmic Skeletons: Structured Management of Parallel Computation. MIT Press & Pitman, 1 edn. (1989)
3. Cole, M.: Bringing skeletons out of the closet: a pragmatic manifesto for skeletal parallel programming. *Parallel Computing* **30** (2004)
4. Ernstsson, A., Ahlqvist, J., Zouzoula, S., Kessler, C.: SkePU 3: Portable High-Level Programming of Heterogeneous Systems and HPC Clusters. *International Journal of Parallel Programming* **49**, 846–866 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10766-021-00704-3>
5. Ha, S., Teich, J.: Handbook of Hardware/Software Codesign. Springer Netherlands, 1st edn. (2017)
6. Hajji, B., Mellit, A., Bouselham, L.: Practical Guide For Simulation And Fpga Implementation of Digital Design. Springer Verlag, Singapor (2022)
7. Lai, Y.H., Chi, Y., Hu, Y., Wang, J., Yu, C.H., Zhou, Y., Cong, J., Zhang, Z.: HeteroCL: A Multi-Paradigm Programming Infrastructure for Software-Defined Reconfigurable Computing. In: Proceedings of the 2019 ACM/SIGDA International Symposium on Field-Programmable Gate Arrays. p. 242–251. FPGA '19, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3289602.3293910>
8. Lai, Y.H., Ustun, E., Xiang, S., Fang, Z., Rong, H., Zhang, Z.: Programming and Synthesis for Software-defined FPGA Acceleration: Status and Future Prospects. *ACM Transactions on Reconfigurable Technology and Systems* **14**(4), 17–39 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3469660>
9. Pacheco, P., Malensek, M.: An Introduction to Parallel Programming. Morgan Kaufmann, 2nd edn. (2020)
10. Steuwer, M., Kegel, P., Gorlatch, S.: SkelCL - A Portable Skeleton Library for High-Level GPU Programming. In: 2011 IEEE International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Processing Workshops and Phd Forum. pp. 1176–1182 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPS.2011.269>
11. Zahran, M.: Heterogeneous Computing: Hardware & Software Perspectives. Association for Computing Machinery, 1st edn. (2019)